

Stabilities and Thermodynamics of Divalent Copper, Nickel, Cobalt and Manganese Complexes with Methylguanidoacetic Acid

R. S. SAXENA and M. K. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur-302 017

Manuscript received 11 August 1981, revised 6 January 1983, accepted 30 March 1983

Complexation of divalent Cu, Ni, Co and Mn with creatine in aqueous medium has been investigated by pH metric titration technique at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$) at 20, 30 and 40°. Formation curves reveal the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in each case. The stability constants of these complexes are determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration techniques as modified by Irving and Rossotti, which are further refined by least square method.

The overall changes in thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the complexation reactions and their relation to electronegativity, ionic radii and stability constants are reported.

SAXENA and co-workers¹⁻⁴ carried out significant investigations on the electrochemical behaviour of some biologically active compounds and their complexation with metals. This communication reports the complexation behaviour of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II) with creatine, and determination of the stability constants of the complexes. Various thermodynamic parameters for the complexation reactions, for which no reference could be located in literature, have also been determined.

Experimental

Methylguanidoacetic acid known as creatine was obtained from B.D.H., England. Other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation. pH measurements were made on an ECIL pH-meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Stability constants :

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.1M) solution :

- (i) 1 ml 0.1M HClO₄ + 2.5 ml 1M NaClO₄.
- (ii) 1 ml 0.1M HClO₄ + 2.5 ml 1M NaClO₄ + requisite volume of creatine solution to give 0.004M ligand concentration in the final solution.
- (iii) 1 ml 0.1M HClO₄ + 2.5 ml 1M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.025M metal salt solution + requisite amount of creatine solution to give 0.004M ligand concentration in the final solution.

The total volume was made upto 25 ml in each case.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti⁵ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL .

By using the titration curves for solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various pH-meter readings were calculated and a curve between \bar{n}_A and pL was plotted to obtain the proton-ligand formation constants of creatine.

Fig. 1. Formation curves for Cu(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Ni(II) complexes of methylguanidoacetic acid at 20°.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 1). From these formation curves, the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$, were calculated which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\bar{n}=1.5$, respectively. The values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) AND CREATINE SYSTEM AT IONIC STRENGTH $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) AT 20, 30 AND 40°

	20°		30°		40°	
	I@	II@	I	II	I	II
Cu(II)						
log K ₁	3.09	3.13	2.99	3.11	2.97	3.02
log K ₂	2.46	2.39	2.25	2.17	2.16	2.12
log β	5.55	5.52	5.24	5.28	5.13	5.14
Ni(II)						
log K ₁	2.99	3.00	2.94	2.96	2.87	2.95
log K ₂	2.47	2.38	2.25	2.26	2.19	2.17
log β	5.46	5.38	5.19	5.22	5.06	5.12
Co(II)						
log K ₁	2.95	2.99	2.92	2.91	2.80	2.86
log K ₂	2.37	2.34	2.32	2.30	2.28	2.25
log β	5.32	5.33	5.24	5.21	5.08	5.11
Mn(II)						
log K ₁	2.93	2.94	2.87	2.90	2.88	2.91
log K ₂	2.35	2.33	2.29	2.31	2.22	2.17
log β	5.28	5.27	5.16	5.21	5.10	5.08

@ I and II represent Irving-Rossotti graphical method and least-square method, respectively. Uncertainty limit upto ±0.02.

Results and Discussion

The values of stability constants of Cu(II), Ni(II) Co(II) and Mn(II) complexes with methyl-guanidoacetic acid obtained by Irving-Rossotti and least-square method at 20, 30 and 40°, recorded in Table 1, show a slight decrease with increasing temperature. It may be noted that the values of stability constants of these complexes are very close and hence it is very difficult to obtain a correct sequence in all situations.

The plot of X_m (electronegativity of metal) against log β (Fig. 2) at 20° shows roughly a linear relationship. It may be mentioned that the stability of metal complexes increases with increasing X_m value which suggests that the metal-ligand bond would be more covalent. Similar observations have been reported by Van Uitert⁷ and Selbin⁸. The plot of log β values at 20° against reciprocal of the ionic radii (Fig. 2) of transition metals shows that the ligand forms the least stable complex with Mn(II) and the most stable complex with Cu(II) in comparison to other transition metals.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming reactions have

Fig. 2. Plots of overall stability constants vs 1-(X_m) electronegativity, and 2-(1/r) reciprocal of ionic radii at 20°.

been calculated at 20° using the relations :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{d \log \beta}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \quad \dots (3)$$

The values are recorded in Table 2. The free energies of formation at 20° (ΔG) follow the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Mn(II), which suggests the decrease in reaction rate also in the same order. Glasstone⁹ has mathematically established that the rate of reaction at a given temperature is determined by ΔG and is often roughly in the order of free energy decrease.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT μ=0.1 M TEMP. 20°

Metal ions	-ΔG (k cal/mole)	-ΔH (k cal/mole)	ΔS (cal/mole/deg.)
Copper	16.84	2.56	48.7
Nickel	16.78	1.93	50.6
Cobalt	16.72	1.34	52.4
Manganese	16.64	1.16	52.8

It is seen that values of change in entropy are positive, which strongly favours the complex formation. The very large entropy change is also justified by considering the greater availability of coordination sites on these metal ions.

By comparing the values of ΔH and ΔS, very small values of enthalpy (ΔH) indicate entropy as the main driving force for formation of metal complexes in aqueous medium. The negative values of ΔH ensure that the reactions are exothermic.

To study the bonding nature of the complexes, it is necessary to observe the relation between ionic radii of metal ions and thermodynamic parameters

ΔG , ΔH and ΔS by plotting them against reciprocal of ionic radii of divalent transition metals. Fig. 3 shows somewhat a linear relationship. Martell⁹ has suggested a dependence of linear relationship between ΔS and $1/r$ for divalent

Fig. 3. Plot of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS against reciprocal of ionic radii ($1/r$) at 20°.

metals. This indicates the predominant role of electrostatic forces involved in ion association processes, a fact which is in harmony with Bjerrum's original ion pair concept.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to the Ministry of Education, New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship to one of them (M.K.S.) and Principal, M. R. Engineering College, Jaipur for facilities.

References

1. R. S. SAXENA and S. P. BANSAL, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1980, 29, 186.
2. R. S. SAXENA and S. P. BANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 831.
3. R. S. SAXENA and G. L. KHANDELWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 757.
4. R. S. SAXENA and A. K. GUPTA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1980, 29, 275.
5. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. L. G. VAN UITERT, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. E. DOUGLAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2736.
7. M. C. DAY and J. SELBIN, "Theoretical Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, N.Y., 1957, p. 114.
8. S. GLASSTONE, "Thermodynamics for Chemists", Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., 1969, p. 286.
9. A. E. MARTELL, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1956, 75, 781.